

NanoPAT Newsletter

November 2020

Online real-time characterisation solutions for
nanoparticle production processes

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Welcome

Dear reader,

NanoPAT project is glad to present our first project newsletter with the main aim of sharing with you our latest technical achievements, introduce our innovative partners and share with the community inputs and curiosities related to nanotechnology and process monitoring.

With this first publication we want to inform you that the [project webpage](#) is already online and if you are interested in the evolution of NanoPAT activities, be it from an academic, business, or other perspective, and would like to closely follow the progress of the project and its outcomes, do not hesitate to contact us on nanopat_coordination@iris.cat and subscribe to our newsletter to receive further information and explore possible collaborations.

As a coordinator I am really glad to lead this cutting edge project that brings together my academic background related to nanoparticle synthesis and my current job focused on innovation in process monitoring technologies.

Furthermore, the active presence of the industries demonstrates the need of further research in this field. Thanks to the deep knowledge provided by the RTOs involved, the project will allow us to overcome the technical hurdles that the market is facing.

In our [newsletter](#) we will provide an update of the project status and we will introduce our consortium partners. Furthermore, we will track special highlights.

On behalf of the NanoPAT project I would like to thank you all for being interested in innovation and technology, asking you to stay tuned during the next 4 years!

Best regards and enjoy the read,

Simona Neri,
Coordinator of NanoPAT

Project summary

In June 2020, the NanoPAT project was successfully kicked-off virtually due to the well known Covid-side effects! This four year project (June 2020 - May 2024) has become reality thanks to the support of the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme. NanoPATs team of 16 EU partners distributed

across 8 European countries will analyse and bring up to TRL6 new online real-time characterisation solutions for nanoparticle production processes. NanoPAT stands for Process Analytical Technologies for Industrial NanoParticle Production.

PATs - Process Analytical Technologies

These are the three novel complementary real-time in situ particle size characterisation technologies (Process Analytical Technologies (PAT)) that are being further developed in NanoPAT:

Photon Density Wave Spectroscopy

An inline process analytical technology capable of calibration-free quantification of light absorption and light scattering in highly turbid, highly concentrated liquid dispersions.

OptoFluidic Force Induction

Photons carry momentum, spin- and angular momentum, not as much to be noticeable in our makro everyday life, but enough for being active in the nanoworld.

TURbidity Spectrometry

A flexible optical technique for monitoring the evolution of suspending particles which size ranges from approx. 100 nm up to few microns.

Case Studies

NanoPAT has a very broad potential for monitoring the synthesis and conversion processes involving an infinite variety of NPs and media types. As a subset representative of this potential, NanoPAT will validate the combination of different nano-characterization technologies in 5 industrial case-studies, demonstrating the viability of the proposed PAT solutions for the industrial NPs production of polymers, silica, hydroxyapatite, zeolites and for the dispersion of ceramic NPs into coatings via electrodeposition method.

Case Study 1

Polymers

Monitoring Particle Formation of Polyurethane dispersions and Polyacrylate emulsions.

Case Study 2

Silica

Real-time in-situ monitoring of the genesis of nanostructured silica under different precipitation conditions.

Case Study 3

Hydroxyapatite

Nanohydroxyapatite particle size characterization using on-line OptoFluidic force induction (OF2i) technology.

Case Study 4

Zeolite

Continuous inline characterization for the manufacturing of zeolites in batch and continuous systems.

Case Study 5

Ceramic

Monitoring of ceramic nanoparticle suspensions in pilot scale production of nanocomposite coatings.

Partner presentations

In this very first issue of our newsletter, we present NanoPAT's Coordinator, IRIS, and NanoPAT's Communication & Dissemination Manager, BNN.

About IRIS Technology Solutions S.L.

IRIS is an advanced engineering company that was established in Barcelona in 2007 and specialises in the manufacture and integration of Process Analytical Technology (PAT)-based real-time quality monitoring solutions for the process industries and IoT systems for smart manufacturing, predominantly targeted at the food, pharmaceutical and chemical industries. In particular, our product line comprises proprietary state-of-the-art IR analysers for at-line and in-line process monitoring.

On the one hand, our solutions are based on the latest developments in photonics, in the fields of MEMs Near Infrared Spectroscopy, Hyperspectral Imaging, and Raman. On the other hand, we leverage ICTs, whereby we apply Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence and Data Mining techniques for predictive and active control, as well as for decision support systems. In addition to photonics-based analysers, we also work

with IoT sensors for enabling equipment and machinery for smart manufacturing and transitioning industry to the Industry4.0 paradigm. Our solutions are cloud-based for mobility, remote monitoring and multi-site applications.

Our Innovation Division which is governed by an Innovation Committee comprising Senior Management, and an Innovation Unit for managing and executing the companies innovation roadmap, has 3 core strategic lines, for shaping the Factory of the Future:

1. New optical photonics-based technologies and PAT systems for production process optimisation
2. ICTs (Artificial intelligence / machine learning, IOT & cloud platforms)
3. Circular and Bio-based Economy: digitalization and waste valorisation

In addition to running an internal R&D programme, as well as carrying out various joint private projects with industry partners, our Innovation Division is highly experienced in working in collaborative R&D projects in H2020 (both as coordinators of >30 FP7 and H2020 projects and partners), and principally in the SPIRE, FoF, and BBI programmes. The company was established in 2007 and currently employs 60+ staff with a turnover of € 5 M. It is equipped with engineering workshops (3), food testing and wet chemistry laboratory, optics labs (2), and an electronics/

telecommunications lab. IRIS is ISO 9001:2008 certified and also is certified under UNE-EN-ISO 166002: Management Systems R&D&i. We are also certified by the local (Catalonian) government as a provider of technological R&D services (Tecnio Certification). IRIS is a member of the following sectorial networks: SPIRE, SPIE, EPIC and SECPHO, in addition to regional industrial collectives such as Smart Space (association of companies and organisations that specialise in the 'smartification' of industry).

About BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (BNN)

BNN is a non-profit research organization owned by the BioNanoNet Association, which currently counts with 60 member organizations that are active in the fields of Health & Safety, Data & Sustainability and Enabling Technologies. In these fields, BNN furthermore coordinates the national technology platforms NanoMedicine-Austria, SusChem-AT and the Austrian Microfluidics Initiative. BNN's mission is to support and guide its members and customers towards a sustainable development of connected technologies with the vision to shape the European high-tech ecosystem to secure a sustainable and prosperous society. By integrating safety, quality and sustainability aspects already in the design phase of a new technology, we support innovative breakthroughs in all sectors. The design process enables us to reach out to the ideal option and find the best solution for each specific use case.

BNN offers its services in four different areas:

Design for Technology Development:

BNN helps you create safe and sustainable processes and products of highest quality. Integrating safety, quality and sustainability aspects already in the design phase of a new technology, supports innovative breakthroughs in all sectors. The design process enables us to reach out to the ideal option and find the best solution for your specific use case. BNN guides you through the Safety-by-Design, Quality-by-Design and Sustainability-by-Design processes.

Innovation Support:

Innovation is the key to everything the future can be. Therefore, by sharing BNN's knowledge within the technological and business field, innovation practices and strategic guidance, BNN will help you on visualizing and getting the fastest way for your idea to become reality and make sure that your innovative effort creates long-term and sustainable value.

Alliances & Clustering:

BNN connects organisations with strategic partners to share and join new initiatives and to national and international strategic stakeholders. BNN establishes and coordinates thematic platforms together and leads initiatives that maximize your impact globally. Through a strategic management of topics of common interests, BNN jointly shapes the R&D&I landscape in Europe.

Complementary Business Support:

BNN helps you to maximize your focus on scientific research, sharing our knowledge and experience as a participant in funded projects on international level! Within the last 15 years, BNN has helped to build and manage small to large scale consortia, and to promote and coordinate dissemination and exploitation activities of research projects at all Technology Readiness Levels. BNN supports in the Project Initiation and Grant Application, Project Management and Communication & Dissemination.

The success of BNN stems from its “network” and the coordination among leading key players from its platform, which is the engine that drives interdisciplinary and innovative processes in these research areas.

Highlights: How NanoPAT began

Testimonial from Dr. Roland Hass, PDW Analytics GmbH, Germany

NanoPAT actually started from earlier research collaboration activities between Potsdam University and ZHAW. There, people very well experienced with European consortia, leveraged this research collaboration, focused on Photon Density Wave (PDW) spectroscopy, into a first initial group of partners from industry and academia. At this very early stage in 2018, Potsdam University was chosen to act as project coordinator, since there the nucleus for the PDW technology is located. Soon, for a real European project, more partners were required: further technology suppliers, research partners from academia, nanoparticle manufacturing plants from industry, dissemination professionals - all with a good mix of SME and large scale.

Due to the great partners and their research activities across European countries, a fantastic consortium could be generated. And it had been a pleasure to move this consortium successfully through the first proposal stage. Due to the temporary employment regulations in German academia, I chose to head for a different employer, and therefore a new coordinator was needed for NanoPAT. And it was absolutely amazing to see how professionally IRIS executed the proposal development for the second and final stage. I am very happy that I could add some part to bring this consortium to reality and I am very much

looking forward to the results we will generate. Particularly for the PDW technology, NanoPAT will be a great chance to move this technology into "reality". When I entered the lab at Potsdam University for the first time as a PhD student, many separate photonic components were spread across the entire room. So, back in those days, it was a PDW research lab but not an individual instrument which could be brought to industrial environments for inline process monitoring. Now, what is special about that technique? In the world of particle manufacturing, actually very few analytical techniques are capable of sizing particles in real-time, under stirred conditions, without sampling or dilution, with low-cost process probes. PDW spectroscopy provides these features and thus promises a completely new insight into manufacturing processes. But since, to the best of our knowledge, only the team in Potsdam does research and development on the PDW technology, it requires time and resources to move from a photonic lab into industrial reality, with its safety, quality, and cost requirements. Here, strong industrial partners are needed to move the PDW technology to the next level and thus gain a strategic benefit for their own added value. The perfect scope for the aims of NanoPAT.

NanoPAT News

[NanoPAT participating in CEN workshop](#)

[NanoPAT at the 14th MeCCE](#)

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